

The Influence of Take and Give Learning Model on Students Learning Outcomes in Subheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Health in Grade V UPTD SDN Pematang Siantar

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A R Q I C L E I N F O

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A B S T R A C T

This research aims to determine the influence of the *Take and Give* Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Clean Air for Health, Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Health in Class V UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School, the method in this research is a quantitative method in the form of an experiment. The research design is pre-experimental type one group pretest-posttest. The population and sample used were 26 students, with two research variables: the dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, and the independent variable (y) in the form of the *Take and Give* model. The data collection technique is the test technique. Test results using the t-test technique with the help of the spss program, based on the results of significant calculations (2-tailed) < 0.05 , namely $0.000 < 0.05$, $t_{count} > t_{table} = 15.256 > 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the *Take and Give* learning model on student learning outcomes in subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School.

INTRODUCTION

Elementary school education is a form of formal educational institution whose national-based education system has a very important role in the development of students. Therefore, education in elementary schools must really provide students with knowledge that can be used as capital to pursue higher education. Education is a process to change a student's identity to be more advanced, the education process in simple language is to change people to be better in knowledge, attitudes and skills. According to Retno (2012:30), education is a conscious and planned process to continue to encourage individual and social change and renewal to achieve a better quality of life, by maximizing students' independence. Educating does not only provide or transfer knowledge, but also includes the process of receiving knowledge, processing it, analyzing it, discussing it and saying it again.

According to Daryanto (2011:1), education is a conscious and systematic effort, carried out by people who are entrusted with the responsibility to influence students so that they have characteristics and habits in accordance with educational ideals. According to Purwanto (2002:10), education is the maturation of students so that they can develop their talents, potential and skills in life. Therefore, education should be designed to provide understanding and improve student learning achievement. According to Djabidi (2016:1), education is the most effective solution for educating individuals, nations and countries. Within its scope, education tries to develop the potential of every human being so that this potential can be useful in the future for the individual, nation and state itself.

Education in elementary school is the most important educational process in the development of students. This is because elementary schools are a source of basic education for children to gain a number of knowledge. The educational program process occurs because of the interaction between educators and students which takes place in learning activities to achieve success in learning, so that the current education system uses the 2013 curriculum. In the learning carried out in schools currently at the elementary school level there is thematic learning. Thematic is integrated learning that emphasizes student participation in learning. This learning involves several basic competencies, learning outcomes, and indicators from several subjects.

Health, there is still a lack of curiosity among students to ask questions or give opinions on material that is not yet understood to the teacher during the learning process, there is no motivation and encouragement in participating in learning, student behavior tends to only listen and record the lessons given by the teacher, students do not want to ask questions let alone express opinions about the material provided. Such conditions will make students feel bored and less than optimal in receiving lessons, which will have an impact on learning outcomes that are less than optimal. Therefore, to overcome this problem, teachers must look for fun learning models and apply them in learning so that students' interest in learning grows and students do not get bored while learning is taking place.

The learning outcomes of students in theme 2 clean air for health, subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD Pematang Siantar State Elementary School are relatively low. 2023/2024 UPTD Pematang Siantar State Elementary School PPKn with KKM 75 only 12 (46%) completed and 14 (53%) did not complete, Indonesian with KKM 75 only 10 (38%) completed 16 (61%) incomplete, SBDDP with KKM 80 only 15 (57%) completed and 11 (42%) incomplete, IPA with KKM 75 only 10 (38%) completed 16 (61%) incomplete, IPS with KKM 75 only 11 (42%) completed, 15 (57%) did not complete.

Apply a suitable learning model. The Take and Give learning model is a suitable learning model to overcome this problem. Because this learning model

requires students to actively collaborate with their partners in the learning process. With the Take and Give model, students will be more motivated because students will play a direct role in conveying and receiving material from their friends.

Using the Take and Give learning model will also be able to overcome learning problems because it will require students to play a more active role in the learning process so that the learning atmosphere will be more enjoyable and being able to make the learning atmosphere active is one way of implementing the Take and Give learning model. Applying the Take and Give learning model can help teachers improve student learning outcomes, apart from that, learning is no longer limited because using this model is expected to influence student learning outcomes and make students much more active when studying. Based on the explanation above, the Take and Give learning model is a learning method that is supported by the presentation of data which begins with giving cards to students which contain material that must be memorized or mastered by each student, then looking for a partner to exchange the knowledge they have. according to the material on the card, then the learning activity ends by evaluating the students by asking for information received from their partner. Based on the explanation above, the researcher is interested in using the Take and Give learning model on the learning outcomes of class V students in theme 2 clean air for health, subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health at UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School.

Problem solving using the Take and Give learning model, especially in lesson theme 2 clean air for health, subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health using a learning model that is considered effective in achieving learning objectives.

To reduce the difficulties experienced by students in learning, observations were carried out, so researchers were encouraged to conduct research with the title: "The Influence of the Take and Give Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Clean Air for Health. Sub-theme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Health in Class V UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Public Elementary School"

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework is a flow of relationships between one concept and other concepts to provide an overview of the variables to be studied. A conceptual framework is useful for connecting a topic to be discussed. Based on observations that the author has made in class V at UPTD SD Negeri Perpipilotan Pematang Siantar, the problem was found that student learning outcomes in learning theme 2 clean air for health, sub-theme 2 the importance of clean air for health is still low, the reason is that the learning process is still teacher-centered. so that students are less involved in the learning process and students do not want to ask questions when the material explained by the teacher is not understood.

To achieve student learning outcomes, the author first gives a pretest to students before learning begins in class V in the form of multiple choice questions to determine students' initial abilities. Next, the author implemented the Take and Give learning model in this class. The learning steps are, the teacher prepares Take and Give cards, the teacher conveys the main material to be studied, after finishing reading the material the students close their books, the teacher gives cards to the students and the students look for their partners and exchange information about each other. material, the teacher provides conclusions, evaluation and closing. Next, the author gave a posttest to students after treatment with the same questions to determine the effect of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The type of research used in this research is experimental research because this research aims to determine the effect of the *Take and Give learning model* on student learning outcomes. The type of research used in this research is quantitative research. Because the data collected is in the form of numbers and the research methods used to research the population or sample in this research, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical in nature with the aim of testing the hypotheses that have been established. (Sugiyono 2018:16).

The experimental research used in this research is Pre-Experiment/form of One Group Pretest-Posttest Design. Where this design has a pretest before being given treatment. So that in this research the results of the treatment can be known more accurately because they can be compared with the situation before being given treatment which is described as follows:

Figure 2 Research Design
One-Group pretest-posttest Design

Information:

O1 = Pretest Score (before treatment)

X = Treatment given

O2 = Posttest value (after treatment)

The population in the research were all students at the UPTD of the Pematang Siantar pilot elementary school, and the samples taken by class V students amounted to 26 students. This research uses a test instrument in the form of multiple choices with the aim of measuring learning outcomes. Before it is used for data collection, the data testing stage uses validity testing, reliability testing, difficulty level testing, and differentiating data testing. In data analysis, the Normality test, Homogeneity test, and Hypothesis test are used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The aim of this research is to determine the influence of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes in thematic learning, specifically theme 2 clean air for health in subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health in V.

Below, data will be presented before and after the research. The data before conducting the research is the question instrument test data, where the tests carried out first are the validity test, reliability test, differential power test and test of the difficulty level of the questions. After the data is valid and reliable, the questions that have been tested on the instrument are suitable for use as tests in research schools. After the questions have been tested and carried out, the data that will be presented after that is descriptive pretest and posttest data, flat pretest-posttest scores, analysis prerequisite tests where the test What was carried out was the data normality test, homogeneity test and hypothesis test, namely *uj-t*.

TEST INSTRUMENT

1. TEST THE VALIDITY OF THE QUESTION

30 questions after the instrument test was carried out at SD Negeri 091626 Bandar Baru, there were 20 valid questions and 10 invalid questions, so that the questions distributed had a total of 20 valid statements. Valid questions can be used for the next test.

2. RELIABILITY TEST

The value of the reliability test results can be seen that r calculated $>$ r table, namely $0.77 > 0.39$ so that the questions are declared reliable and included in the high category.

3. TEST THE LEVEL OF DIFFICULTY

Analysis, which is used to examine test questions and their difficulty. The level of difficulty was obtained with the help of Microsoft Excel 2010 with a level of difficulty of $0.00 < P < 0.30$ difficult; $0.30 < P < 0.70$ moderate; $0.70 < P < 1.00$ easy So you can get which questions are in the difficult, medium and easy categories.

M shows that of the 30 questions tried out, they are classified in the easy category, namely 20 questions (questions no. 1,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,12,14,15,19,20,21,22, 23,24,25,26 and 28), 9 questions with a medium level of difficulty, namely (questions no. 2,11,13,16,17,18,27,29,30) and a difficult level of difficulty, namely 1 question namely question number 3.

4. TEST THE DIFFERENTIAL POWER OF THE QUESTION

Shows that of the 30 questions there are 12 questions with sufficient criteria and 17 questions with good criteria.

DATA ANALYSIS

1. NORMALITY TEST

The Normality Test is carried out to determine whether the *Pretest* and *Posttest data* from the sample is normally distributed or not. The results of the Normality test use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method in the SPSS Version 26 program. The basis for decision making is that if the significance level is >0.05 , then the student data values are normally distributed and if on the contrary the significance level is <0.05 then the student data values are not normal, the data obtained are as follows:

**Table 1 Normality Test
Tests of Normality**

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pretest (Conventional)	,224	26	,002	,918	26	,040
Posttest (TAG Model)	,203	26	,007	,929	26	,074

Based on table 4.9 above in the One Sample Shapiro-Wilk Test Output, it can be seen that for 26 students the significant pretest score was $0.40 > 0.05$, meaning the pretest data was normal. And the significant *posttest value* is $0.74 > 0.05$, which means the posttest data is normal.

2. HOMOGENEITY TEST

The Homogeneity Test is used to determine whether several data population variants are the same or not. The test was carried out with the help of SPSS version 26 *For Windows*. With the criteria, testing if the significance value is > 0.05 then it can be said that the variance of the two data is the same. The following homogeneity test results can be seen in the following table.

**Table 2 Homogeneity Test Results
Test of Homogeneity of Variances**

Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
,115	1	50	,736

Based on the results of the homogeneity test above, it can be seen that the significance value for the Homogeneity test is 0.736. The significance criterion is > 0.05 , so it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest scores have the same homogeneous variance.

3. HYPOTHESIS TEST

Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine the positive and significant influence of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes in subtheme 2, the importance of clean air for health in class V, which can be seen from the following table:

Table 3 Hypothesis Test (t test)

		Paired Differences					t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Posttest (TAG Model) - Pretest (Conventional)	32,308	10,792	2,116	27,949	36,667	15,265	25	,000

Based on the table above, the significant value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , namely $0.000 < 0.05$, $t_{count} > t_{table} = 15.256 > 0.05$, then $H_0(0)$ is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes in subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School.

Discussion

This research was carried out in class V UPTD of SD Negeri Perpilotan Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year from 14 October - 24 October 2023. The population used was all students of class V UPTD of SD Negeri Pilot Pematang Siantar with a sample of class V students of 26 students.

In this section, the results found in the research that have been carried out will be described. The intended results are conclusions drawn based on the data collected and data analysis that has been carried out. This research aims to determine the influence of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes in Subtheme 2. Before carrying out the research, the research first carried out instrument trials at the same level with different schools, namely at SD Negeri 091626 Bandar Baru, Dagang . The trial was carried out in order to determine the number of questions out of 30 questions that would be tested in multiple choice form and find 20 valid questions.

Based on the Pretest results, the average student learning outcome score was 50.58 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Take and Give Model was relatively low. Furthermore, the average value of the Posttest results is 82.88. So after using the Take and Give learning model, students had better learning outcomes than before using the Take and Give learning model. After carrying out the Pretest and Posttest Normality test, then a Homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the Homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.736 was obtained. Based on predetermined criteria, if the sig value is > 0.05 , the data is said to have homogeneous

variation. In this case it can be seen that $0.736 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the data has the same characteristics or is homogeneous.

After the Normality test and Homogeneity test have been fulfilled, proceed to the Hypothesis test. From the student test results, it was calculated that it was 15.256 and the t table was 1.725. Thus, $t_{count} > t_{table} = 15.256 > 1.725$, which means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is an influence of the Take and Give learning model on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD students at Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School for the 2023/2024 academic year.

From the research above, it can be concluded that there has been a significant increase in student learning outcomes by 34% in sub theme 2 the importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD of Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School using the Take and Give learning model. This research is supported by previous researchers who carried out by Yusransal et al (2001), Bela Putri Amelia (2022) and Elawati et al (2022). Based on previous researchers using the same model, the discussion above in this research shows the influence of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes. This model can be applied at UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School to improve student learning outcomes, especially in theme 2 clean air for health, subtheme 2 the importance of clean air for health.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research conducted on class V students at UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School for the 2023/2024 academic year. The data obtained can be concluded that in general the use of the Take and Give learning mode has a great influence on the learning outcomes of class V students at UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School. The increase in learning outcomes can be seen from the increase in student learning outcomes which were initially measured before going through the learning process through the average Pretest activity, namely 50.58. After going through the learning process using the Take and Give learning model, another Posttest was given to determine the students' final abilities, the average score increased to 82.88.

Based on hypothesis testing with a significance level = 0.05 and t table of 1.725. Thus, $t_{count} > t_{table} 15.256 > 1.725$, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Take and Give learning model on learning outcomes in Subtheme 2, the importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School. So based on the results of the Hypothesis test, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is a significant influence of the Take and Give learning model on learning outcomes in Subtheme 2, the importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School.

FURTHER STUDY

From the research results, it is known that the influence of the Take and Give learning model on student learning outcomes, Subtheme 2 The importance of clean air for health in class V UPTD of Pematang Siantar Pilot Elementary School for the 2023/2024 academic year, so the researchers provide the following suggestions:

1. For students, they can use the Take and Give learning model as a way to develop students' abilities.
2. For teachers, they can use the Take and Give learning model in this research as an alternative way of learning to improve student learning outcomes.

3. For researchers, they can apply the model in this research as an effort to improve student learning outcomes when they become teachers.
4. For schools, they can improve the model in this research on different materials or subjects.

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